

Review of the Policy Element for the Research Data Management Framework for Institutions

An implementation project for the Institutional Underpinnings Program

Project summary report

University of New England

February 2023

About the Institutional Underpinnings Program

In partnership with 25 Australian universities, we created a jointly-agreed Research Data Management Framework for Institutions for the management, sharing, retention and disposal of research data. Each partner university conducted projects to validate and test an aspect of the framework in their local contexts. This is a report on one of the projects.

More information

View more outputs of the [Institutional Underpinnings program](#).

View the [Research Data Management Framework for Institutions](#).

Project Summary

At University of New England (UNE), the entire organisational policy framework is undergoing significant review. This includes a plan to move from a large policy library to a superstructure of under 10 overarching policies, and an expanded suite of procedural and roadmap supporting documents.

Due to the timing of this large-scale policy structure review, it was necessary to strip back the commencement of the research data management (RDM) policy review process to a review of the [Research Data Management for Institutions Framework](#) Policy element by the team of UNE experts assembled to complete the framework policy element review and subsequently commence the RDM policy and supporting documents review. The team was comprised of experts from university research, IT, records, governance and library services, and a specialist academic committee.

Throughout 2022, this project suffered a number of setbacks for a range of reasons external to the project. As such, in May of 2022 the project coordinator re-assembled a RDM Policy Review team to continue the project in a stripped-back format under the guidance of a streamlined leadership group. The plan to access consultancy services to assist with moving forward with a policy document review was dropped in light of the entire Policy Structure review being undertaken by UNE and the development of a data classification system which would be required before the RDM policy review could begin.

A thorough consideration, commentary and review of the framework Policy element was undertaken, by considering the current policy and associated documents and the current committee structure and pathways of consultation within UNE.

Resulting Improvements

The process of reviewing the framework policy element has helped UNE prioritise the formation of its own team of experts who will now move on to undertake a review of the RDM policy and supporting documents.

UNE's involvement in the Institutional Underpinnings project has promoted and instilled the importance of gathering its research data expertise, and confirmed the essential collaborative nature of such work. UNE is reducing the silo-ing, or compartmentalising of aspects of RDM. The process has helped clarify UNE's direction and responsible roles in the RDM space, removing inefficiencies such as separate divisions doing the same task in two different ways.

While UNE is still in its initial phase of RDM policy review, the process of reviewing the framework policy element has pushed this policy review to the fore, with the Policy and Governance team providing support and reassurance in the prioritisation of this review in the current restructure of the policy system.

Next Steps

The Policy review will occur next with the current team of expert's efforts being guided and coordinated by the University Library. Supporting documents will be reviewed and restructured by the team alongside the policy review. A roadmap to implementation will be developed alongside the Policy and supporting documents. These will be shared via UNE's online [document library](#) upon completion and publication.

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